

HYBRIS

Enhanced Hybrid Storage Systems

PROJECT

A new generation of battery-based hybrid storage solutions for smarter, sustainable and more energy efficient grids and behind-the-meter systems.

High-quality and technologically innovative batteries are key to reach the goals of the European Green Deal and contribute to the zero-pollution ambition set in it. We are a 3-year European project that brings together 15 partners from 6 countries to develop a novel battery enabled hybrid storage system. These advanced batteries are aimed to become a more viable and sustainable solution to enhance electric grid stability and support renewable energy use.

A Dual System for Energy Storage

TECH

The novel Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS) developed by our project is based on battery hybridization: HYBRIS will be twinning at system level Lithium Titanate batteries (LiTO) and Aqueous Organic RedOx Flow Battery (AORFB). These storage technologies will be coupled with a breakthrough Battery Management System, Novel Power Electronics and an advanced Power Management System that are fully integrated with Energy Management Systems (EMS) and Grid Systems. These innovations are the groundwork for the optimization of an advanced hybrid storage solution for microgrid applications that is high-performing, cost-effective and environmentally-friendly.

HESS Core Concept and Battery Technologies

We propose the combination of high power and fast response performant lithium ion battery based on LTO and an Aqueous Organic Redox Flow batteries, free of metals, as an environmentally friendly solution to be the energy supplier workhorse of this hybrid configuration.

Advanced Battery Management System and Power Electronics

Advanced Battery Management System (ABMS) is a diagnostic & prognostic solution for HESS health management supporting improved maintenance and optimal operation of the combination of AORF Li-ion Battery Energy Storage System (BESS).

Hybridisation: Optimal Sizing and System Integration

A set of technologies, tools and methods specifically designed for the integration of hybrid energy storage system. It includes the SHAD integration technology package, the Power management system and the optimal sizing and validation by HIL (Hardware-in-the-loop) based Digital Twin.

High Level Control & EMS / Replication

Our innovative, cloud-based Energy Management System (EMS) will centralise all the information and models to optimize the bids and assets handling. This enables a faster, real operation and better storage technology selection for power and energy applications targeting BTM and FTM segments.

The Impacts

IMPACTS

- Increased competitiveness of electrical energy storage by **balancing power needs with energy needs**.
- Providing a more efficient system with a longer and better performing lifespan with an **Round Trip Efficiency (RTE) above 90% for LiTO and above 75% for AORFB**, and expected lifetime above 12 years.
- Optimizing balance-of-plant and installation costs with a **reduction of 15-40 % in CAPEX and 20-40 % in OPEX**.
- Project results should put the energy storage cost on the path to fall **below 0.05 €/kWh/cycle by 2030**.
- Replication potential** validated via 3 pilot sites.

Our Pilot Sites

PILOTS

Messina, Italy

Partners: SOLIDARITY AND ENERGY SPA - SAE
Use Case Application: Local residential energy community integrated in island grid
Potential Outreach: Local civic network (30+ entities), other national and international partners in the ASSIFERO and REVES networks. More than 100 photovoltaic plants in Sicily island (about 1 MW total power)

Den Hague, Netherlands

Partners: 4YEF, ILECO
Use Case Application: Deployment of energy services in private grids (Business park)
Potential Outreach: Approx. 50-100 SME business parks across the Netherlands

Brasschaat, Belgium

Partners: Quares, ILECO
Use Case Application: E-mobility hub with multipurpose EV charging with integrated PV generation
Potential Outreach: In total approx. 10-50 SME business parks across Belgium

Discover who we are and how we will help build the electric grid of tomorrow.

<https://hybris-project.eu/>

@HybrisEU

/company/hybris-project

Member of the FLORES Network

This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 963652.